

Gram scale continuous flow synthesis of silver-on-silica patchy particles with widely tunable plasmon resonances

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ABSTRACT. Extensive research has been conducted on colloids that incorporate nanostructured noble metals, motivated in particular by their highly tunable optical properties. However, the lack of approaches that offer reproducibility, tunability and scalable production is limiting their exploitation in many application areas. Here we present a novel approach for the controlled

formation of silver patches on silica spheres using gold nanocrystal seeds. The synthesis of the seeds and their attachment in very small numbers to the silica spheres is achieved without employing any surfactants, stabilizers or linker molecules. Using advanced transmission electron microscopy techniques, we show that electroless deposition of silver occurs at the introduced seeds and leads to a central protrusion from the metal patches not observed in earlier, seed-free work. We demonstrate both seeding and growth processes can be achieved in millimixer flow reactors. With this simple and scalable approach we provide compelling evidence for the use of seeds in producing targeted morphology and function. Specifically, patch size and optical properties can be tailored in a predictive manner by adjusting the density of seeds on the silica core particles as well as reagent concentrations during growth. As a result, our process can be used to obtain colloidal dispersions with localized surface plasmon resonance peaks anywhere in the range 400 nm to nearly 1300 nm. We confirm the scalability of our method by operating the growth process for around 70 minutes. Apart from changes in the first few minutes, the product properties remained rather stable and over a gram of high quality silver patch coated silica could be recovered. Our approach opens up exciting new avenues for applications which require larger amounts of plasmonic or anisotropic nanoparticles with tailored morphology and optical properties.

Introduction

Colloids containing nanostructured noble metal components have been intensively studied over the past decades due to their highly effective interaction with light^{1,2}. Depending on the size, shape, composition and placement of the metal, aspects which can now be impressively controlled on the lab scale,^{1,3-12} optical properties can be engineered across the visible and infrared electromagnetic spectral regions.^{13,14} This opens up, in theory, a wide range of potential uses including sensing and

spectroscopy,^{10,15-20} therapy,^{21,22} and photothermal systems,²³⁻²⁵ (electro/photo)catalysis,^{7,26-29}, solar technology³⁰⁻³² and pigments³³⁻³⁷. Nevertheless, the exploitation of colloidal plasmonic nanostructures in many of these applications is limited by a lack of scalable and reproducible approaches for their production. This results from a major limitation of most liquid phase techniques to produce noble metal nanostructures with non-spherical morphologies: their reliance on surfactants and other additives to promote symmetry breaking,³⁸ as well as the need for a deep awareness of the “variety of synthetic details and nuances”³⁹ that should be under practical control. While much work has been carried out to improve the more robust synthetic protocols,^{37,40,41} there is still a great need for new approaches involving a minimal number of process steps, requiring few reagents, avoiding functional ligands but at the same time enabling localized surface plasmon resonances (LSPR) to be tuned over a wide spectral range. In 2011, we introduced a single step electroless plating process for the formation of thin silver patches on silica spheres.⁴² Our approach was based on the Tollens reaction and unlike earlier recipes to coat colloidal silica with silver we used non-functionalized core particles.⁴³ Moreover, the silver growth, which took place laterally over the curved silica surface did not require any surface-active ligands to direct the patch morphology. The driving force for the unusual crystal growth which we observed was coulombic due to the attraction of the silver ion, provided in rather low concentration, to the anionic core particle surface and the exclusive generation at that location of the necessary supersaturation for metal nucleation and growth.⁴⁴ Inspired by the simple process and range of silver patch structures and optical properties which could be achieved we demonstrated how the mixing-limitation of our original batch reaction could be overcome in a continuous flow millimixer environment.⁴⁵ This development opened the route to reproducible and scalable synthesis. Production yields of several grams with such a setup can, in principle, be achieved in a straightforward manner by running the

process for a sufficiently long time. Recently, we could show how a possible problem with this, namely ageing of the reagent reservoirs over long periods, could be mitigated.⁴⁶ Nevertheless, one very significant limitation of our approach results from its extreme simplicity. Performed as a single step, the electroless deposition conditions which result from the initial reagent concentrations define both the nucleation and growth rate. Thus, attempts to control the amount of growth in order to obtain silver patches with targeted size invariably lead to an unwanted influence on the nucleation conditions and thus result in undesirable numbers and sizes of patches on the silica cores or even a large fraction of bare cores.⁴⁷ Through use of a cascaded two-T mixer process and making use of the kinetic control afforded to the reaction by the ammonia concentration we were able to partially separate nucleation from growth, but not sufficiently for control of patch size.⁴⁶ Such control is however essential in order to design arbitrary patchy particle morphologies for application as anisotropic building blocks,⁴⁸ or, as already noted above, to achieve a wide tunability of the LSPR. To address this issue, here we explore whether silver patch nucleation can be directed by using seed nanocrystals and without compromising significantly on process simplicity and scalability. It should be noted that while seeding is already long established for the synthesis of complete metal nanoshells,⁴⁹ and has even been realized using continuous flow processing,⁵⁰ the objective there is to decorate the functionalized core particles with as many seed nanocrystals as possible. In the present case, we set out to do almost the exact opposite – to attach (ideally) one single seed nanocrystal to a non-functionalized silica core. We show that such seeding can be achieved rather simply, making use of the destabilization of a mixture of anionic core and seed particles in continuous flow. We go on to demonstrate how silver patches can be grown from the seeds using our previously developed millimixer approach and illustrate how patch size and optical properties can be tailored in a predictive manner simply by tuning the reagent

concentrations. Finally, we demonstrate the scalability of our method, producing over a gram of patchy particles without significant change in the properties of the product over most of the production run.

Results and Discussion

The main objective of the present work was to introduce a seeding step prior to silver patch growth in order gain greater control over the patch size. The basic idea was to use one or more small metal nanocrystals previously attached to the core silica particle as growth-initiating seeds. A key boundary condition was that the silica particle surface should not be changed by the seeding process. Moreover, to maintain scalability, the number and complexity of processing steps should not be greatly increased. At the outset, we identified two approaches for achieving this goal: (1) heterocoagulation of cationic metal seeds with the anionic silica cores and (2) coagulation of a mixture of anionic metal seeds and anionic silica cores following the addition of salt. The challenge with (1) is the lack of simple methods involving low cost ligands for the reproducible synthesis of small cationic metal nanoparticles. While we could develop a proof-of-principle seeding protocol based on the heterocoagulation of spermine-functionalized gold nanocrystals and the silica cores, this required the gold seed to be freshly functionalized before each coating run due to low stability of the cationic sol. However, for systematic studies and production runs, it is preferable to produce a stock of seeded cores which can be stored for weeks or months. For this reason, we found approach (2) considerably more effective and thus we focus here only on that method. A particular advantage is that it allows us to use ligand-free gold nanocrystals, which are naturally anionic, as seeds. Therefore, we selected the simple borohydride reduction approach of Deraedt et al. which provides a stable sol without additional stabilizers.⁵¹ TEM measurements of the seeds revealed

spheroidal particles with a mean diameter of around 5-7 nm (see Figure 1a and corresponding size distribution in Figure S1a in the Supporting Information). However, UV-VIS spectrophotometry measurements showed a clear red shift and increase in extinction of the LSPR peak over time, indicating ripening of the colloid (Figure S1b). We therefore estimated the nanocrystal size, at the time of use for seeding, using the simple spectral analysis reported by Haiss et al.⁵² That analysis circumvents the insensitivity of the LSPR peak wavelength to nanocrystal size by considering the ratio between the extinction value for the peak to that of the valley which appears at 450 nm. The authors verify the validity of their analysis for gold nanocrystals as small as 5 nm and confirm that even down to 3 nm the equation can provide acceptable estimates.⁵² For our system, it yielded a very smooth trend in nanocrystal size over time (Figure S1c). While this method likely reports a different size to that from TEM, it is not feasible for a routine process to rely on microscopy every time it has to be performed. Moreover, we cannot rule out that TEM sample preparation leads to additional ripening effects in these extremely small, ligand free nanoparticles.

Knowledge of the nanocrystal size was critically important for the seeding process as it allowed us, assuming stoichiometric consumption of the entire gold precursor, to determine the number concentration N_{AuNC} , of the gold nanocrystals at the time of seeding. Knowing also the number concentration of silica particles N_{SiO_2} we could define the seeding density $\rho_{0,seed}$, where the integer “0” indicates that the seeding density is a ratio of particle numbers, and distinguishes from a mass ratio, for which the integer would be “3”.

$$\rho_{0,Seed} = \frac{N_{AuNC}}{N_{SiO_2}} \quad (1)$$

The parameter $\rho_{0,Seed}$ enables simple comparison of the seeding process and resulting patchy particles for core particles with different size, shape or chemical composition.

Figure 1. (a) HAADF-STEM image of a typical batch of gold nanocrystals used for seeding in the present work. The sample for microscopy was prepared approximately 5 days after synthesis. (b) HAADF-STEM image of a silica spheres with gold nanocrystals attached via continuous flow seeding. A seeding density, $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 20 was used. (c) Magnified image of the region marked in (b) with a red rectangle (d) EDX analysis of the particle in (c) showing Au net intensity signal at the nanocrystal position.

As mentioned above, the seeding strategy we followed is based on the salt-induced coagulation of a mixture of gold nanocrystals and silica core particles. Due to the fact that the individual colloidal dispersions exhibit a negative zeta potential of -47.9 mV and -48.6 mV, respectively, it was possible to mix them together without heterocoagulation occurring. According to the well-known DLVO theory, the electrostatic barrier to coagulation between two particles with a surface charge of the same sign decreases with increasing ionic strength of the medium. Therefore, we expected that at a sufficiently high salt concentration the van der Waals attraction between the core

and seed particles would result in the gold nanocrystals adhering to the silica particles. Here, we would be assisted by the roughly two orders of magnitude larger diffusivity of the gold nanocrystals compared to that of the silica. This makes it more likely for a gold nanocrystal to collide with a silica particle than two gold nanocrystals with each other, thus enabling a good distribution of the seed among the cores. Nevertheless, to ensure as rapid a rise in ionic strength across the whole sample, we implemented the seeding process with a continuous flow T-mixer (see Figure 2, upper part) with inlet flowrates corresponding to a mixing time of 187 ms as determined by the method of Commenge and Falk.⁵³ As salt to raise the ionic strength, we selected potassium nitrate. On the one hand, potassium ions do not specifically adsorb to either material. On the other hand, the anion is identical to that of the metal precursor used in the patch growth and so is already compatible with that reaction. Small-scale batch tests showed that a potassium nitrate concentration of 180 mM was sufficient to trigger the adsorption of the gold nanocrystals to the silica core but only resulted in weak flocculation of the latter. Thus, we used this salt concentration in the present work.

Following mixing of the gold nanocrystal and silica core particle suspension with the potassium nitrate solution in the T-mixer a pinkish layer formed at the bottom of the collection container after some minutes (see Figure S2). Since homocoagulation of the gold nanocrystals would lead to a pronounced colour change (pink to blue⁵⁴) this observation confirmed that the gold seed was successfully immobilized on the silica core particles. This was also directly verified by TEM measurements in which gold nanocrystals could be only found on the silica spheres and not scattered over the substrate.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the seeding (upper part) and patch growth (lower part) continuous flow processes for the synthesis of silver patches on silica core particles. SiO_2 refers to core silica particles, AuNCs to gold nanocrystals and s-SiO₂ to gold nanocrystal seeded silica core particles.

To establish if silver patches could be controllably grown on seeded silica core particles, we used the latter in place of bare silica in our previously developed continuous flow process (Figure 2, lower part).⁴⁵ Figure 3 shows extinction spectra and SEM images for samples produced at four

values of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ and under identical silver deposition conditions. Low magnification images of the same samples can be found in the Supporting Information (Figure S3).

Figure 3. (left) Extinction spectra and (right) SEM images of silver patches grown in a continuous flow process under identical conditions on silica spheres that had been seeded with gold nanocrystals at four different seeding densities $\rho_{0,Seed}$. Corresponding low magnification images, including one of the $\rho_{0,Seed} = 5$ sample can be seen in Figure S3 in the Supporting Information.

A clear influence of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ on the position of the main extinction peak, corresponding to the patch in-plane dipole resonance, is visible. As $\rho_{0,Seed}$ decreases from 40 to 10 the peak red shifts from around 875 nm to 1150 nm before it disappears entirely for a $\rho_{0,Seed}$ value of 5. A similar result to the latter case was obtained with non-seeded core particles (data not shown). This suggests that at low $\rho_{0,Seed}$ insufficient gold nanocrystals are present to initiate growth and due to the low

reaction temperature of 30 °C, the conditions needed for the kind of heterogeneous nucleation seen on bare silica particles in our earlier work are not present.^{42,44,46} Besides higher order in-plane resonances in the range 500-700 nm which shift similarly to the main dipole peak, a further feature in the extinction spectra for the cases of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ between 10 and 40 can be seen at a constant wavelength value of around 331 nm. This peak was observed in our earlier studies with silver patches and corresponds to the out-of-plane quadrupole resonance, similar to that seen for flat silver nanoprisms.^{41,55} Since this feature depends almost exclusively on the patch thickness,⁴⁷ we can conclude that the value of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ has rather little influence on that aspect of the patch morphology. It follows that for a lower seeding density the coverage of patches should increase. In other words, when more silver is available to add to each patch, since patch thickness remains roughly constant for all values of $\rho_{0,Seed}$, the patch will spread laterally even further. These inferences from the extinction spectra are verified by the SEM images in Figure 3 and Figure S3. While the patches are clearly distributed in size, the samples having a higher $\rho_{0,Seed}$ possess generally smaller patches. These increase in coverage for lower $\rho_{0,Seed}$, corresponding to the red shift of the dipole resonance seen in the extinction spectra. The number of visible patches per particle is also seen to decrease from around 7-8 for $\rho_{0,Seed} = 40$, to around 3-4 for $\rho_{0,Seed} = 20$ and to around 1-2 for $\rho_{0,Seed} = 10$. As already inferred from the extinction spectra, the sample with $\rho_{0,Seed} = 5$ had no identifiable patches (Figure S3). Even accounting for patches hidden from view and the size distributions of the core and seed particles it would appear that $\rho_{0,Seed}$ overestimates the actual number of seed nanocrystals attached to the cores by a factor of around 5. This could be explained by incomplete reduction of the gold precursors during seed synthesis, a systematic error in our (optical) determination of the gold nanocrystal size, losses of the gold nanocrystals during the seeding process or through their aggregation.

It should be noted that the samples shown in Figure 3 were produced by using seeded silica that had not been previously washed i.e. to remove the potassium nitrate introduced during seeding or potentially non-adsorbed gold nanocrystals. In fact we found that washing the seeded silica dispersion by repeated cycles of centrifugation and redispersion, prior to silver patch growth, is undesirable. As shown in Figure S4, the patches grown on the washed seeded silica are larger and more broadly distributed and have their dipole LSPR beyond 1300 nm, the measurement limit for aqueous dispersions. This suggests that a certain number of seed nanocrystals were removed from the silica cores during washing. Since that process would be very hard to control, we preferred the use of non-washed seed. In that case the patch number is roughly proportional to $\rho_{0,Seed}$ as we have seen above. Interestingly, we found that the size of patches grown on non-washed seeded silica slightly depends on the time between seeding and patch growth. For reproducible results we used one week aged seeded silica cores. In a future study, we will look more closely at this seed ageing phenomenon, which, if understood, could be a further means to tune the product properties.

Another interesting feature, which can be seen in the SEM images in Figure 3 and Figure S3, is a protrusion at the center of the patches. Since this was not observed in our earlier work based on the non-seeded, batch or continuous heterogeneous nucleation and growth approach,⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ we conclude that this feature results from the silver adding isotropically to the seed nanocrystal. However, as we have previously shown, lateral growth of the patch over the silica core is generally favored over radial growth due to the electrostatic attraction of silver and silver-ammine complex cations to the anionic silica surface. Consequently, the growth of the central protrusion appears to be limited. In order to investigate this feature and the overall patch morphology in greater detail, we carried out STEM tomography on selected patchy particles produced at $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 20. Figure

4a shows one exemplary HAADF-STEM image from a tomographic tilt series (see Movie S1 in the Supporting Information for the full tilt series) with several patches on a silica sphere, most of them possessing a clearly visible central protrusion. The 3D volume reconstruction (see Movie S2) confirms this and at the same time reveals the individual morphology of the patches. One exemplary reconstructed patch is visualized in Figure 4b (see also Movie S3) which highlights the shape and position of the central protrusion. The overall thickness of the patches and the protrusion can be directly characterized via slicing through the reconstruction perpendicular to the silica surface at the center of the protrusion, as demonstrated in Figure 4c. In that case, we measure the roughly 130 nm wide patch to have an approximately 35 nm diameter central protrusion, and a patch thickness of approximately 32 nm at the center and 8-10 nm at its edge.

To verify that the central protrusion originates from the gold nanocrystal seed, we carried out STEM-EDX on a number of patches. As Figure 4d-f shows, it was possible to identify single gold-rich regions at the base of a typical silver protrusion at the center of a patch. We also occasionally observed multiple seed nanocrystals within a patch (see Figure S5). This confirms that at least some of the seeding points correspond to aggregated gold nanocrystals. As noted above, this is one explanation for the fact that we always obtained fewer patches per core particle than the selected value of $\rho_{0,seed}$. In a future article, we will report on a detailed study of the patch crystal structure and how the morphology and aggregation state of the seed nanocrystals can influence it.

Figure 4. Advanced TEM characterization of silver patches on a silica core from a sample that had been seeded with a seeding density $\rho_{0,Seed} = 20$ prior to patch growth. a) Exemplary image from a HAADF-STEM tilt series of one silica sphere covered with several Ag patches, each revealing a central protrusion (see Movie S1 for the full tilt series). The patch highlighted in purple is shown as b) a surface rendering (see also Movie S2) and c) a slice through the 3D reconstructed volume (see also Movie S3). d) HAADF-STEM image of another exemplary Ag patch from the same sample and corresponding EDX maps of the e) Au and f) Ag net intensity signal in the region of the central protrusion indicated in d) as a blue rectangle.

Having demonstrated that the seeding of silver patch growth functions as we intended and that the seeding density can be used as a means to control the patch size, we next carried out a systematic study of how growth reaction parameters for constant values of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ influence the

product optical properties. To this end, we varied the silver nitrate and seeded silica concentration in the range 50-150% of the values used in the samples shown in Figure 3 and for $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 10, 20 or 40. Normalized extinction spectra for $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 40 and an overview of the trends in the dipolar LSPR wavelength for all seeding densities are shown in Figure 5. Extinction spectra of the samples produced with $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 20 and 10 can be seen in Figure S6.

Figure 5. a) Normalized extinction spectra of silver on silica patchy particle dispersions produced from seeded silica with seeding density $\rho_{0,Seed} = 40$ and variation of relative SiO₂ (top) or AgNO₃ (bottom) concentration in the patch growth process, b) Plots of dipolar LSPR peak wavelength versus SiO₂ or AgNO₃ concentration for the three seeding densities used. Note that 100% relative concentration corresponds to the concentrations used in the initial experiments (see Figure 3 and corresponding text).

This data clearly shows how, for a given seeding density, systematic variation of the seeded core particle (Figure 5a top) or silver nitrate concentrations (Figure 5a bottom) leads to corresponding shifts of the dipolar LSPR. For increasing seeded silica concentration the peak blue-shifts while for increasing silver nitrate concentration the opposite behavior is seen. As shown in Figure 5b, the range of accessible dipolar peak wavelengths depends on the seeding density, a higher value of $\rho_{0,Seed}$ leading to shorter wavelength peaks and vice versa. Since the choice of the latter, as well as the seeded core particle and metal precursor concentrations will define the amount of silver available per seed nanocrystal, we re-evaluated the data in Figure 5b with respect to that parameter, which we define with the dimensionless ratio n^* :

$$n^* = \frac{n_{Ag}}{n_{AuNC}} = \frac{c_M(AgNO_3) \cdot N_A}{c_0(s-SiO_2) \cdot \rho_{0,Seed}} \quad (2)$$

where n_{Ag} and n_{AuNC} are the number concentrations (in L^{-1}) of silver atoms and gold nanocrystals respectively, $c_M(AgNO_3)$ is the molar concentration of silver nitrate, $c_0(s - SiO_2)$ the number concentration of seeded silica core particles and N_A the Avogadro constant.

Figure 6a (top) shows the dipolar peak wavelength data from Figure 5a replotted versus the corresponding n^* values. This graph indicates that the resonance wavelength correlates rather linearly with the amount of silver available to each seed nanocrystal. This is a remarkable result as it shows that the plasmon resonance position can be systematically designed in our simple surfactant-free synthetic process. The process operator just needs to choose suitable combinations of seeding density and growth solution concentration, the absolute values of which can be chosen from a wide range.

We next consider how reproducible the n^* versus dipolar LSPR position trend is when different gold nanocrystal seed batches are used. At the same time we explored if the linear trend mentioned

above applies at even lower n^* . Figure 6a (bottom) shows a plot of this data for a number of studies using four different gold nanocrystal seed batches, and between them, four values of $\rho_{0,seed}$. Figure S7 shows SEM images of selected patchy particle samples produced over a wide range of n^* . It is worth recalling here that $\rho_{0,seed}$ depends on the particle size and corresponding particle number concentration of the original gold nanocrystal sol, something which evolves over time due to ripening and which is determined using a simple spectroscopic analysis rather than microscopy. Moreover, as we have seen above, there is a systematic error between the calculated value of $\rho_{0,seed}$ and what is actually obtained in terms of numbers of patches per core. Despite these considerable uncertainties, the lower plot in Figure 6a shows a clear global trend and charts out a means with our process to access plasmon resonances over a range of more than 800 nm, spanning the whole visible spectrum and part of the near infrared. Interestingly, there is a kink in the trend at an n^* value of around 1×10^6 . For values below this, the peak wavelength varies with a steeper gradient than above it. This suggests that a change in the patch morphology takes place as more silver than a certain threshold amount becomes available for each seed nanocrystal. As shown in Figure S7, the patches at lower n^* values are very small and rather conical due to limited lateral spreading compared to the central protrusion. However, for n^* above 1×10^6 any influence of the central protrusion is masked by the significant growth of the patch over the core particle surface. Due to the corresponding plasmon peaks in the visible spectrum, values of n^* below 1×10^6 are particularly significant for the synthesis of colored dispersions and pigments. To underline the possibilities here, in Figure 6b we show a photograph of nine samples prepared using Seed C and by systematically varying n^* between 0.025×10^6 and 0.81×10^6 . Although it is well known that plasmonic colloids can exhibit these kinds of colors, we believe this is the first time that such

a wide range has been achieved in a single process and without mixing dispersions of different colour.^{34,56}

Figure 6. a) Dependence of the dipolar LSPR wavelength on the amount of silver per seed nanocrystal (n^*). Top: Data from the samples shown in Figure 5b (Seed A). The solid line represents a linear fit. Bottom: Data for various patchy particle synthesis series using different seed batches and seeding densities. The data for each seed batch and seeding density combination are fitted with a linear function. b) Photograph of patchy particle dispersions produced using Seed C and n^* between 0.025×10^6 and 0.81×10^6 .

Returning to the lower plot of Figure 6a, we note that there is some batch-to-batch variation in the optical properties obtained even for similar values of n^* . Specifically, deviation in the slope and scatter of the data is seen with samples using different seed batches or with different $\rho_{0,Seed}$ (groups with same colour and symbol type). For instance, for identical values of n^* , coatings on silica seeded with the same seed but with a $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 40 have dipole peaks that are 50-100 nm red shifted compared to those with a $\rho_{0,Seed}$ of 20. Moreover, using different seed batches but with identical n^* and $\rho_{0,Seed}$ further variations can be seen. There are several factors which may contribute to the observed deviations. Besides the variability of the mixing process used to produce the seeded cores, and the post-seeding ageing phenomenon mentioned already, the patch morphology and resulting optical properties may depend on the average size, size distribution and aggregation state of the gold nanocrystals at the time of patch growth. For instance, in the lower plot of Figure 6a, the sizes of the gold nanocrystals used for the $\rho_{0,Seed} = 40$ samples were, at the time of seeding, 3.8 nm (green, downwards pointing triangles) and 4.3 nm (yellow, upwards pointing triangles). Moreover, for a given n^* , the distance between adjacent patches on a single core particle will decrease with increasing $\rho_{0,Seed}$. This could lead to electromagnetic coupling of the patch LSPRs and corresponding red-shifting of the peaks. While we have opted for a simple, but rather uncontrolled seed synthesis approach in the present work focused on demonstrating the large range of optical properties achievable, in the future we plan to explore systematically the influence of seed size and shape using monodisperse gold nanocrystals and employing electrodynamic simulations to identify the effect, if any, of inter-patch electromagnetic coupling.

A major advantage of our process, besides the ability to tune the dipole LSPR peak position over a wide range, is that it can, in principle, be run for a long time in order to produce a large amount of product. To demonstrate that this is possible we adapted our setup to include large volume

reagent reservoirs and product-collection containers (Figure 7a). We then seeded 1.6 g of core particles with gold nanocrystals, leading to a $\rho_{0,Seed}$ value of 40. Due to the high flow rate used, it required only 2 minutes to complete the seeding. In the subsequent patch growth process, which was carried out with reagent concentrations corresponding to $n^* = 0.996 \times 10^6$, a total volume of 8.5 l was produced in approximately 70 minutes. In earlier work employing non-seeded continuous flow synthesis, we noticed that over such durations the dilute ammonia solution used can absorb carbon dioxide, leading to a pronounced change in the patch morphology.⁴⁶ Moreover, we found that intentionally lowering the pH with nitric acid can, to some extent, mitigate this effect. Therefore, in the present case we included 1 mM nitric acid in the same reservoir as the ammonia (R2 in Figure 7a). Following synthesis, we allowed the dispersion to settle over a number of days and then decanted it into smaller containers to facilitate washing. Finally, we could obtain 1.2 g of dry patchy particles (Figure 7b).

Interestingly, we observed slight variations in product morphology and optical properties over the course of the scaled up synthesis. Figure 7c shows an SEM image of the initially produced material while in Figure 7d the same can be seen for the product leaving the reactor at the end of the process. Figure 7e shows the extinction spectra for these, plus intermediate samples and the final obtained product. It appears that the largest spectral change, an ~ 80 nm blue shift, occurred in the first minutes of the synthesis run. Comparison of the SEM images suggests that this shift may be related to a very slight thickening and narrowing of the silver patches. However, we cannot be certain at this stage if the differences seen following washing, drying and insertion into the SEM vacuum are as pronounced as what they would have been in the liquid phase. In any case, due to the complexity of the samples, quantitative analysis of the differences in patch size based on these images is prohibitive.

Figure 7. a) Photograph of the setup used for the gram scale synthesis of silver patches on seeded silica nanospheres. 1) Reservoir (R1) containing gold nanocrystal seeded silica, silver nitrate and formaldehyde, 2) Reservoir (R2) containing ammonia and nitric acid solution, 3) peristaltic pump, 4) heated water bath, 5) static T-mixer where flows from R1 and R2 are combined, 6) Product collection canister. Not visible in the photograph in water bath 4) are the stainless steel reagent heating tubes and polyamide residence time reactor tubes. b) Photograph of approximately 1 gram of silver-silica patchy particles, c) SEM image of the product collected at the start of the scale up run, d) SEM image of the product collected after 70 minutes of the scale up run e) UV/VIS/NIR extinction spectra obtained for samples collected during the scale-up run and for the final product.

Future work, supported by electrodynamic simulations, will look more closely at possible changes in the product morphology during the startup of the process, which could be a result of the equilibration of the reactant solutions or of the tubing of the continuous flow reactor. Moreover, we will examine how this effect can be eliminated through process developments, or mitigated by aiming the synthesis towards a longer wavelength LSPR peak position than the one actually desired. It is also our longer-term objective to introduce a feedback loop into our process which instructs the reagent pumps to adjust their flowrates to maintain the LSPR peak at a defined location.

Conclusion

In this work, we have described a significant improvement in the tunable and scalable colloidal synthesis of noble metal-containing nanostructures compared to both our earlier work and that reported in the literature. In a significant enhancement to our previously established continuous flow process for the electroless deposition of thin silver patches on silica nanospheres, we showed that addition of a seeding step prior to patch growth can enable the facile tuning of the morphology and optical properties. The seeds used were gold nanocrystals produced by a simple borohydride reduction reaction and were attached at a very low seeding density to the silica core particles via salt-induced coagulation carried out in a rapid continuous flow mixing process. We then subjected the seeded silica to the same continuous flow electroless deposition process which we developed previously, albeit at the lower temperature of 30 °C. In contrast to the earlier work, which relied on heterogeneous nucleation of patches on non-seeded silica at 50 °C, we showed here that silver only grows if sufficient seeds are present. Moreover, we used energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy to identify the presence of gold seeds within the silver patch and showed with electron tomography how seeded growth can produce a morphological feature in the form of a

central protrusion not observed for heterogeneously nucleated patches. With the seeding of silver patches established, we demonstrated how the patch size and optical properties can be tailored by changing the seeding density, the seeded core particle concentration or the silver precursor concentration. Using these parameters to define a dimensionless ratio of silver atoms to seed nanocrystals, we identified a trend in the dipolar localized surface plasmon resonance wavelength that was relatively insensitive to the absolute values of concentrations used. This enables quite significant flexibility in choice of process parameters in order to tune resonance peaks between 400 nm and nearly 1300 nm. Finally, we showed how the continuous flow patch growth process can be operated for over one hour on a large batch of seeded core particles. The optical properties of the product only changed significantly during an equilibration phase of around 5 minutes and remained quite stable after that. After downstream processing, more than 1 gram of silver patch coated silica powder could be recovered.

Having established continuous flow seeding followed by continuous flow patch growth as a powerful method for the production of large amounts of plasmonic particles with tailored anisotropic morphology and optical properties, we aim to use the process to assist with completing our understanding of the patch growth mechanism. On the one hand, we will soon report on inline spectroscopic studies of the kinetics of patch growth under transport and reaction limited conditions. On the other hand, we will carry out a systematic study of the effect of nanocrystal seed size, shape and aggregation state. Moreover, the means to produce grams of patchy particles afforded by our newly established process will enable us to apply it to fields where such materials have rarely seen large scale investigations e.g. plasmonic pigments, photocatalysts, Pickering emulsions or stationary phase materials for multimodal chromatography.

Experimental Section

Materials. The silica particles used in this work were obtained from Merck KGaA (Monospher M500, 483 nm mean diameter determined by SEM analysis of more than 3000 particles). All other chemicals used were purchased from Carl Roth GmbH & Co. KG: formaldehyde (37% aqueous solution, methanol stabilized), aqueous ammonia solution (32%), silver nitrate ($\geq 99\%$), potassium nitrate ($\geq 99\%$), tetrachloroauric(III) acid trihydrate ($\geq 99.5\%$), sodium borohydride ($\geq 97\%$) and nitric acid ($\geq 65\%$). Using an ultrapure water system (PureLab Flex3 from ELGA LabWater, Veolia Water Technologies Deutschland GmbH), stock solutions of AgNO_3 (100 mM), HAuCl_4 (10 mM), KNO_3 (360 mM) and HNO_3 (0.1 M) were prepared and used over several weeks. NaBH_4 (50 mM) and NH_3 (2%) solutions were freshly prepared before each set of experiments. Formaldehyde was used as purchased. Core particles were dispersed as a 5 mg/ml suspension prior to seeding.

Synthesis of gold nanocrystals. Gold nanocrystals with sizes in the range 3-5 nm for use as seeds were produced by the simple method reported by Deraedt et al. in which tetrachloroauric(III) acid is reduced by sodium borohydride.⁵¹ We selected a molar ratio of these reagents of 1:10 as this results in a sol that shows high colloidal stability for many months even without additional stabilizers. Briefly, in a typical synthesis 0.5 mL of a 50 mM solution of NaBH_4 was rapidly added under vigorous stirring to 24.5 mL of a 102 μM aqueous solution of HAuCl_4 . The solution immediately turned red, indicating the formation of gold nanocrystals. The thus produced colloidal suspensions were stored in sealed bottles in the dark. For each batch of gold nanocrystals produced, the optical extinction spectrum was regularly acquired for a time span starting immediately after the synthesis up to several weeks. This enabled the rapid estimation of the mean particle size x_{UV-VIS} using the equation reported by Haiss et al.:⁵²

$$x_{UV-VIS} = e^{3.0 \cdot \frac{E_{LSPR}}{E_{450nm}} - 2.2} \quad (3)$$

where E_{LSPR} and E_{450nm} are the extinction value at the peak position and 450 nm respectively.

Seeding process. Gold nanocrystals produced as described above and aged for at least 3 days were used for seeding silica particles. During seeding, a stock containing 4 mg/ml SiO₂ particles and a certain volume of the gold nanocrystal dispersion was mixed with a 360 mM solution of potassium nitrate (Figure 2, upper part). Both liquids were delivered by a double-channel syringe pump at 200 ml/min per channel through polyamide tubing with an inner diameter of 3 mm to a polyamide T-mixer with an inner diameter of 2 mm. The characteristic mixing time of the T-mixer had previously been determined by the Villermaux-Dushman reaction (reagent set 1 and Equation 17 in reference [53]) to be 187 ms. The seeded material was stored in the dark and was used over several weeks or months. For reproducible patch growth we used seeded silica that had been stored for at least 7 days. Although the seeded silica particles sedimented over time they could be redispersed by gentle shaking or magnetic stirring.

Continuous flow synthesis of patchy particles. The synthesis of patchy particles from the seeded silica particles was achieved by mixing flows from two 30 mL reservoirs (Figure 2, lower part). In the standard synthesis the first reservoir contained the seeded silica particles (s-SiO₂ 180 mg/L) in an aqueous solution of silver nitrate (120 μM) and formaldehyde (161.16 mM). The second reservoir contained a 68 mM aqueous ammonia solution. While the formaldehyde and ammonia concentrations were fixed throughout this work, we varied the concentration of seeded silica and silver nitrate. Moreover, we varied whether the seeded silica was used as prepared or pre-washed. Table S1 in the Supporting Information gives details on the specific concentrations used for the samples shown in the figures discussed in this article.

Using a multi-channel peristaltic pump (Reglo ICC, Cole-Parmer GmbH) the contents of the two reservoirs were pumped with 60 ml/min per reservoir through stainless steel coils immersed in a heating bath at 30°C and 3 mm inner diameter polyamide tubing into a polyamide T-mixer with inner diameter of 2 mm. After passing a 5 m long, 3 mm inner diameter polyamide residence time tube, the product was collected. The initial 20 mL to leave the reactor tube after the product became colored was discarded. The following 30 mL was collected directly in a vial already containing sufficient sucrose stabilizer in order to achieve a final concentration of 20 wt%. The product which left the reaction tube after this was discarded.

Characterization. UV-VIS-NIR extinction spectra of gold nanoparticles and patchy particles were obtained using Lambda 35 and Lambda 950 spectrometers from Perkin Elmer Inc. respectively. For measurement of patchy particle dispersions a reference solution with the corresponding concentration of sucrose was used. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) was performed on gold nanocrystals directly dried from the liquid dispersion. Samples of patchy particles for scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and TEM were prepared by washing 3 times with ultrapure water and deposition on a silicon wafer (SEM) or lacey carbon supported copper grids, 200 mesh (TEM), and allowed to dry under ambient conditions. SEM images were recorded on a Gemini Ultra 55 (Carl Zeiss AG) operating at 10 kV acceleration voltage. The following high-angle annular dark-field (HAADF) scanning transmission electron microscopy (STEM) measurements were carried out on a FEI Titan Themis³ 300 at 300 kV. HAADF-STEM tomography was performed with a conventional tomography holder from Fischione, model 2020, covering a tilt range of 140° in 1° steps with a STEM semi-convergence angle of 1.2 mrad, a camera length of 91 mm (collection angle range of 61 to 200 mrad), dwell time of 2 μs and a resolution of 2048 x 2048 pixel with a pixel size of 0.85 nm. Energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy

(EDX) analysis was performed using Thermo Fisher Scientific Velox software version 3.0.0.815 with multi-polynomial background correction for each element. The tomographic data was reconstructed with a model based iterative reconstruction (MBIR) algorithm,⁵⁷ in which the HAADF signal was inverted. Particle size distributions from TEM or SEM images were determined using image analysis with the software ImageJ.⁵⁸ Zeta potential measurements were carried out on a Zetasizer Nano ZS instrument (Malvern Panalytical Ltd). Here, pure water and 1 mM KCl solution were used as diluents for the gold nanocrystals and silica cores respectively so as to enable the analysis to proceed according to the Hückel (gold) and Smoluchowski (silica) approximations.

ASSOCIATED CONTENT

Supporting Information.

The following files are available free of charge.

Table of synthetic parameters used in this work, additional micrographs, photographs and UV/VIS extinction spectra (PDF)

HAADF-STEM tilt series, 3D volume reconstruction and 3D slice movies (MP4)

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The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

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